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Some Aspects of Goalkeeping and Goalscoring in Football

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Abstract :

Some aspects of goalkeeping and goalscoring in the game of Football are discussed in this study from physical and mathematical points of view. For goalkeeping, the taller goalkeeper has a reach advantage over the shorter goalkeeper and is therefore better equipped to deal with high balls. However, it is shown from the falling rod problem in physics that the shorter goalkeeper is able to fall a fraction of a second quicker than the taller goalkeeper and is better able to clear low balls. As for goalscoring from a close range, the solid angles subtended by the goal area at the strike location is taken as a measure of effectiveness of a strike. The solid angles are calculated for ground kicks, aerial side kicks and bicycle kicks and headers from high, low and average heights. The aerial kicks and headers have greater solid angles than the more common ground kicks and are therefore more likely to score from a geometrical point of view. Generally speaking, ground kicks can be executed with greater precision and power, but the goalkeeper also has a better anticipation of their directions. It is more difficult for the goalkeeper to predict the strike location of a header (or an aerial kick) in air (a three-dimensional space) and the subsequent direction of the ball, which makes that strike an even more dangerous one.

1. Introduction :

The *goalkeeper* is perhaps the most important player in a Football (Soccer) team. The quality of goalkeeping often decides the outcome of a Football game. Among the attributes of a goalkeeper are his or her height, strength, flexibility, reflex, good vision and jumping and diving abilities. The heights of the first-choice goalkeepers in the English Premier league range from 6'0" (1.83 m) to 6'6" (1.98 m) with an average height of 6'3" (1.92 m) [1, 2]. The heights of the goalkeepers in the other professional leagues as well as international matches are also very similar [1].

On the other side of goalkeeping, goalscoring is even more important, since a clean sheet of goalkeeping can ensure a draw but not victory. The two basic methods of scoring a goal are: (1) *kicking the ball with the foot*; and (2) *heading the ball*. Most goals are made by kicking, but many, especially from close range are made by heading. The vast majority of kicked goals are made from the ground level. But on rare occasions, *side kicks* and *bicycle kicks* are made when the ball is in flight. Also, headed goals can be classified into *low*, *average* and *high headers* according to the level of the strike.

In this study, we analyze some aspects of goalkeeping and goalscoring. We first address the relative advantages of the taller and shorter goalkeepers, including the times of descent to the ground in stopping ground strikes. Next, we analyze the relative advantages between ground kicks, aerial kicks and headers. We employ physical and mathematical considerations to address these issues.

2. Goalkeeping by Taller and Shorter Goalkeepers :

We first address the question of relative advantages or disadvantages of the taller and shorter goalkeepers having representative heights of 1.98 m and 1.83 m, respectively. It is axiomatic that *the taller goalkeeper has the reach advantage of stopping the high balls over the shorter goalkeeper*. As regards the low ground balls, there is no obvious answer. We can tackle this problem by applying physics principles to goalkeeping.

We model the diving goalkeeper by a uniform rod of mass m and length l pinned at the lower end and allowed to fall under gravity, with l representing the height of the goalkeeper. By the principle of conservation of energy, we have:

$$\frac{1}{2} I \left(\frac{d\theta}{dt} \right)^2 + \frac{mgl}{2} \cos\theta = \frac{mgl}{2} \quad (1)$$

where θ is the angle the rod makes with the vertical and I is the moment of inertial of the rod:

$$I = \frac{1}{3} ml^2 \tag{2}$$

Substituting Eq. (2) in (1), one gets the angular velocity of the rod:

$$\frac{d\theta}{dt} = \sqrt{\frac{3g}{l} (1 - \cos\theta)} \tag{3}$$

Separating the variables and employing a trigonometric identity, we have:

$$dt = \sqrt{\frac{l}{6g}} \operatorname{cosec} \frac{\theta}{2} d\theta \tag{4}$$

In principle, the time of free-fall of the rod from the vertical position is:

$$\tau = \int_0^\tau dt = \sqrt{\frac{l}{6g}} \int_0^{\pi/2} \operatorname{cosec} \frac{\theta}{2} d\theta \tag{5}$$

However, *the lower limit of the θ -integral yields a singularity* (a lively discussion can be found on the Web [3]). In reality, *it is easier and faster for the goalkeeper to incline himself to a small angle of 15° or $\pi/12$ radian (say) from the vertical and let gravity complete the fall.* In that case, Eq. (5) is replaced by:

$$\tau = \sqrt{\frac{l}{6g}} \int_{\pi/12}^{\pi/2} \operatorname{cosec} \frac{\theta}{2} d\theta \tag{6}$$

Equation (6) is readily obtained from an on-line integral evaluator [4] to give:

$$\tau = \sqrt{\frac{l}{6g}} \left[-2 \log \left(\cot \frac{\pi}{4} \right) \right]_{\pi/12}^{\pi/2} \tag{7}$$

Upon setting the limits, we arrive, in SI units:

$$\tau = -\sqrt{\frac{2}{3g}} \log \frac{\cot^{\pi/8}}{\cot^{\pi/48}} \sqrt{l} = 0.48086\sqrt{l} \quad (8)$$

The time taken by the goalkeeper to descend to the ground is proportional to the square root of his height! In other words, the shorter goalkeeper falls to the ground slightly faster than the taller goalkeeper. The times of descent for the 1.98m and 1.83m goalkeepers as calculated from Eq. (8) were 0.6766s and 0.6505s, respectively. This 3.86% difference does represent a small but significant advantage to the shorter goalkeeper. Given *Galileo's discovery that all objects free fall at the same rate under gravity* (in the absence of air-resistance), this is a surprising result!

In summary, *the taller goalkeeper has a decisive advantage of stopping high balls, whereas the shorter goalkeeper has a small but significant advantage of stopping ground balls.*

3. Goalscoring by Ground Kicks and Aerial Strikes :

The goal is a rectangular area bounded by two 8' high vertical posts, a 24' wide crossbar, and the goal-line below, enclosed by the goal-net behind. A goal is scored when the ball enters the goal from the front. In this section, we discuss the relative effectiveness of goalscoring from a close range by kicked balls and headed balls. We consider the various modes of striking the ball: (1) *kicking from the ground*; (2) *side kick from a height of 3'*; (3) *bicycle kick from a height of 4'*; (4) *low header from a height of 4'*; (5) *average header from a height of 5'*; and (6) *high header from a height of 6'* (Table I). We assume that all the strikes are made from a distance of 24' in front of the middle of the goal (Fig. 1). The effectiveness of a strike is determined by the *solid angle subtended by the goal area at the strike location*.

The general expression for the solid angle subtended by a rectangular area at an arbitrary location is found in the literature [5]. In Fig. 1, the goal area of width a (24') and height b (8') is situated in the $y-z$ plane of a rectangular coordinate system, with the left post at a distance c from the z -axis, and the goal line at a distance of d above the y -axis. The strike location is placed at a distance x from the origin. The elementary solid angle $d\Omega$ subtended by an element $ds = dydz$ of the goal area at the strike location is given by:

$$d\Omega = \frac{dscos\theta}{r^2} = \frac{dydz}{x^2+y^2+z^2} \frac{x}{\sqrt{x^2+y^2+z^2}} \quad (9)$$

Hence the total solid angle subtended by the goal area is

$$\Omega = \int d\Omega = \int_{y=c}^{a+c} \int_{z=d}^{b+d} \frac{x}{(x^2+y^2+z^2)^{3/2}} dydz \quad (10)$$

Since x is fixed, we write

$$\Omega = x \int_{y=c}^{a+c} \left[\int_{z=d}^{b+d} \frac{dz}{(x^2+y^2+z^2)^{3/2}} \right] dy \quad (11)$$

Now

$$\int_{z=d}^{b+d} \frac{dz}{(x^2+y^2+z^2)^{3/2}} = \left| \frac{z}{(x^2+y^2)\sqrt{x^2+y^2+z^2}} \right|_d^{b+d} \quad (12)$$

Placing the limits in Eq. (12) and substituting in (11), we get

$$\Omega = x \int_{y=c}^{a+c} \frac{(b+d)dy}{(x^2+y^2)\sqrt{x^2+y^2+(b+d)^2}} - x \int_{y=c}^{a+c} \frac{ddy}{(x^2+y^2+d^2)} \quad (13)$$

Upon carrying out the integrations, one arrives at the desired solid angle

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega = & \tan^{-1} \frac{(a+c)(b+d)}{x\sqrt{x^2+(b+d)^2+(a+c)^2}} - \tan^{-1} \frac{c(b+d)}{x\sqrt{x^2+(b+d)^2+c^2}} \\ & - \tan^{-1} \frac{(a+c)d}{x\sqrt{x^2+d^2+(a+c)^2}} + \tan^{-1} \frac{cd}{x\sqrt{x^2+d^2+c^2}} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

We can now proceed with calculating the solid angles for the six types of strikes from close range (Table I). For the sake of simplicity, the strikes are assumed to be taken in front of the goal in the vertical plane bisecting the goal area: $c = -12'$. The distance d is chosen to represent the six different strikes: $d = 0$ for the ground kick; $d = -3'$ for the side kick; $d = -4'$ for the bicycle kick and the low header; $d = -5'$ for the average header; $d = -6'$ for the high header. The strike range is the same for all six types of strikes: $x = 24'$.

The results are shown in Table I. The solid angle was the highest for the bicycle kick and the low header (0.2944 steradian); followed by the side kick and the average header (0.2937 steradian); high header (0.2917); and the ground kick (0.2838 steradian) in that order. This means that, the ***solid angle is the highest for the elevation equal to half of the height of the goal posts*** and diminishes above and below that elevation. The solid angle is the lowest for the ground kicks. In general, ***the solid angle is larger for the headers and aerial kicks than the ground kicks.***

4. Revised Solid Angles :

There is a physical effect which further increases the solid angles for the headers and aerial kicks over ground kicks. This can be called the '***bounce effect***', which is that an aerial strike below the goal line can still end up in the net if it bounces within a narrow strip of ground (of 3' ft, say) in front of the goal line. Figure 2 shows the geometrical configuration of this effect which effectively increases the goal height of the strike. Here, AB represents the goal post, having a height: $z = 8'$; CD represents the strike elevation h ; and BE is the width of the narrow strip = 3'. From the similar triangles BEF and CED : $dz = h/7$; whence dz , the ***effective increase of the goal height*** is (1) 0.85' for the 6' high header; (2) 0.71' for the 5' average header; (3) 0.57' for the 4' low header and bicycle kick; and (4) 0.43' for the aerial side kick. The ***effective goal height*** for the four strikes then becomes 8.86', 8.71', 8.57' and 8.43' respectively. The resulting revised solid angles for the strike elevations are calculated and entered in Table I. The high header now has the largest solid angle followed by the average header, low header / bicycle kick and the side kick in that order. The solid angle for the ground kick remains the same. ***The increase in solid angle is directly correlated to the elevation of the strike!*** This effect further enhances the solid angles for the aerial strikes (headers and aerial kicks) over ground kicks.

A couple of further observations related to the ground kicks and aerial strikes can be made qualitatively. First, ground kicks can be made with greater power and directional accuracy than aerial strikes. However, the goalkeeper can also better judge the directionality since the human eye is naturally trained to observe motions on the ground (a two-dimensional space). It is more difficult for the goalkeeper to guess the strike location in air (a three-dimensional space) as well as the flight path of the ball prior to the strike. Also, it is more difficult to control the direction of

the aerial strikes, but that only adds to the uncertainty for the goalkeeper. On the balance, these effects also tend to make the aerial strikes more dangerous than the ground kicks.

5. Concluding Remark :

Goalkeeping and goalscoring are two of the most important aspects in the game of Football (Soccer). In this paper, we have demonstrated how the principles of physics and mathematical analysis could be applied in these areas. Whether the results are entirely convincing are left to the readers, and more importantly, to the football fans and football players themselves.

Table I : Solid Angle subtended by Strike at Goal

Strike Type	Elevation, ft.	Solid Angle Ω , steradian	Revised Ω , steradian	Remark
Ground Kick	0	0.2838	0.2838	most common
Aerial Side Kick	3	0.2937	0.3087	rare
Aerial Bicycle Kick	4	0.2944	0.3147	rare
Low Header	4	0.2944	0.3147	common
Average Header	5	0.2937	0.3194	common
High Header	6	0.2917	0.3229	uncommon

Figure 1

Figure 2

References :

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